

RARE EARTH IONS FARADAY GYROMAGNETIC EFFECT OF Eu³⁺ IN CRYSTALS

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Annotation: The studies on the frequency dependence of the Faraday effect and the obtained results are of interest to understand the mechanisms of the formation of the Faraday effect in magnetic crystals, and the theory that takes into account the great importance of the contribution of MD-transitions in NE-ions to FE calculations are shown. The results of the study of the frequency and temperature dependence of the Faraday effect of EuGaG garnets of European composition are of great importance in solving problems related to the synthesis of new magnetic materials with high magneto-optical originality.

Key words: Faraday effect, Faraday effect formation mechanisms, MD-transitions, garnets of European composition, EuGaG system, frequency and temperature dependence of Faraday effect, Van-Flekovski.

INTRODUCTION

According to Shen's analysis, the expression for Faraday's magneto-dipole effect can be written in the following form:

$$\alpha_F^m = \frac{\pi\omega \cdot e^2 N\alpha}{mc} \cdot \sum_{a,b} \left[\frac{(\omega + 1/2 \cdot i\tilde{A}_{ab}) / \omega_{ab}}{(\omega_{ab}^2 - \omega^2 + 1/4 \cdot \tilde{A}_{ab}^2) - i\omega\tilde{A}_{ab}} \right] (f_{ba}^+ - f_{ba}^-) \quad (1.1)$$

where $f_{ba}^\pm$ is equivalent to the average value of the refractive index in the Lawrence approximation; - power of the MD transition oscillator from state |a> to state |b> s with energy for two circularly polarized waves[1-9].

On the other hand, the oscillator strength can be expressed as:

$$f_{ba}^\pm = (2m\omega_{ba} / \hbar e^2) \cdot |\langle j | \frac{1}{2i} \hbar \cdot [(\vec{l} + 2\vec{s}) \times \vec{k}]_\pm | a \rangle|^2 \cdot \rho_a^0 \quad (1.2)$$

Here and π are the orbital and spin moments in the corresponding case;

$\vec{k}$ is the light wave vector; ρ_a^0 - the ground state of a magnetically active ion is occupied by the boson. (3.2) expression

$$f_{ba}^{\pm} = (2m\omega_{ba} / \hbar e^2) \cdot |\langle j | -i[\vec{n} \times \vec{M}]_{\pm} | a \rangle|^2 \cdot \rho_a^0 \quad (1.3)$$

We rewrite it in the form, where - z axis is a unit vector directed along the magnetic field H ||;

$$\vec{M} = -\left(\frac{e\hbar}{2mc}\right) \cdot (\vec{l} + 2\vec{s}) = -\mu_B(\vec{l} + 2\vec{s})$$

-ion magnetic moment; μ_B - Boron magneton. Components of vector multiplication

$$[\vec{n} \times \vec{M}]_{+} = \hat{M}_{-} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\hat{M}_x - i\hat{M}_y) \quad [\vec{n} \times \vec{M}]_{-} = \hat{M}_{+} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\hat{M}_x + i\hat{M}_y)$$

RESULTS ANALYSIS

In the longitudinal Zeeman geometry: $m = (m_1)$, S_m is the Van-Flekovski "inserted" parameter in the external magnetic field N.

$$\langle J_0 m | \mu_B(\hat{L}_z + 2\hat{S}_z)H | (J_0 \pm 1)m' \rangle = \langle J_0 m | \mu_B \hat{S}_z H | (J_0 \pm 1)m \rangle \quad (1.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_m &= \langle Jm | \hat{S}_z | (J+1)m \rangle = \langle (J+1)m | \hat{S}_z | Jm \rangle \\ &= -\langle Jm | \hat{L}_z | (J+1)m \rangle = -\langle (J+1)m | \hat{L}_z | Jm \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

Thus, the frequency-independent temperature dependence of the "gyromagnetic" Verde constant in paramagnetic compounds doped with Eu³⁺ ions is not determined by the analogous dependence c(T) of the magnetic susceptibility of Eu³⁺ ions, which is presented in Fig. 16 and (1.4) and (1.3) calculated from expressions c(T) and c(T) temperature dependences are clearly visible from graphical comparisons. This comparison shows that the case of the "gyromagnetic" Verde constant determined by the function c(T) differs from the corresponding temperature dependence of the Eu³⁺ ion magnetic susceptibility c(T), especially in the temperature range above 100 K.

In the supplementary figure in a EuGG single crystal measured in the crystallographic direction at a temperature of 300K in a constant magnetic field of N = 9.0 kE at a wavelength of 500 -800 nm (as well as at laser wavelengths of 632.8 nm and 1150 nm) Spectral dependence of FE is presented.

CONCLUSION

According to the results of [9], the spectral dependence of the constant of the trivalent (NE) rarer European ion Verde V(Eu³⁺) in the range of light frequencies removed from the resonance frequency of the separated 4f-5d transitions is given. Where the first term represents the contribution to the Faraday cycle of magneto-optically active (ED) electro-dipole transitions in

$\lambda_{\text{EuGG}, 0} = 250 \text{ nm}$ is the “effective” wavelength of allowed ED transitions occurring in Eu^{3+} ions in the garnet structure .

References:

1. Belov K.P. Redkozemelnyye magnetiki i ix primeneniye. - M: Nauka,1980. – 239 p.
2. Zvezdin A.K., Matveyev V.M., Mukhin A.A., Popov A.I. Redkozemelnyye iony v magnitouporyadochennykh krystalax. - M: Mir, 1985. - 294 p.
3. Krupichka S. Fizika ferritov i rodstvennykh im magnitnykh okislov. - M: Mir, 1976. – 353 p.
4. Yelyashevich M.A. Spectrum redkix ground. - M: Gostexizdat, 1953. – 456 p.
J.H. Van Vleck // Phys.Rev. 41 -1932- p.208.
5. Shats P.N., McCaffrey A.D. Faraday effect. //Uspehi khimii.-1971.-vol. 11, No. 9.- S.1698-1725.
6. Zvezdin A.K., Kotov A.V. Modern magneto-optics and magneto-optical materials (Bristol and Philadelphia: IOP Publishing, 1997), p. 386.
7. Stephens P.J. Magnetic circular dichroism // Advan. Chem. Phys. - 1976. V.35. - R.197-264.
7. Saitkulov F. E. et al. 2, 3-Dimethylquinazolin-4 (3H)-one //Acta Crystallographica Section E: Structure Reports Online. – 2014. – T. 70. – №. 7. – C. o788-o788.
8. Saitkulov F. et al. TITRIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM CATION IN "MEGATON" VARIETY OF CABBAGE //International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 134-135.
9. Sapaev B. et al. Synthesis of 2-methylquinazoline-4-thione with the purpose of alkylation of 3-propyl 2-methylquinazoline-4-thione with alkylating agents //AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing LLC, 2022. – T. 2432. – №. 1. – C. 020009.
10. Boymuratova G. O. et al. To Examine the Processes of Biochemical Action Of 6-Benzylaminopurine with Cobalt-II Nitrate Dihydrate on the “Morus Alba” Variety of Moraceae Plant //Eurasian Journal of Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics. – 2022. – T. 3. – C. 39-42.
11. Sapaev B. et al. Study of methylation reactions of 2-phenylquinazoline-4-tion with “soft” and “hard” methylation agents and determination of its biological activity //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – T. 258. – C. 04023.

12. Valiev U.V., Gruber J., Burdick G. Magneto-optical Spectroscopy of the Rare-Earth Compounds: Development and Application. - USA (Irwin), 2012, 139 p.
9. Judd BR. Optical absorption intensities of rare-earth ions // Phys. Rev. - 1962. - V.127, No. 3 - P. 750-761

